

Interaction of Sulphur Dichloride with Substances Containing the Reactive Methylene (-CH₂) Group or Substituted Methylene Group.

BY

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The work was undertaken with a view (1) to study the reactivity of the hydrogen atoms of a methylene group situated between two carbonyl groups as in the case of substituted amides of malonic and methyl malonic acid, and (2) to throw light on the debated and vexed question of the constitution of sulphur dichloride.

The existence of a definite compound of the composition, SCl₂, has been repeatedly called in question (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1870, 23, 455; 1871, 24, 1163, *Compt. rend.*, 1878, 86, 664; *Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1886, 45, 867). SCl₂ has been regarded by some as a solution of chlorine in sulphur monochloride and by others as a compound in the state of partial dissociation. Costa (*Gazzetta*, 1890, 20, 367) determined cryoscopically the molecular weight of the reddish brown liquid obtained by saturating the monochloride with chlorine below 0° and then removing the excess of chlorine by a current of carbon dioxide. The results of the determinations of molecular weight in benzene and in acetic acid solutions agree with the formula SCl₂. This view was challenged by Ruff and Fischer

(*Ber.*, 1903, 36, 418) who assert that they got no evidence of the existence of the compound SCl_2 when they examined the composition of the liquid and the vapours at temperatures between -10°C and 0° . Böeseken (*Rec. trav. chim.*, 1905, 24, 209) obtained diphenyl sulphide by the interaction of sulphur dichloride with benzene in the presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride at 0° . This supports the view that at low temperatures sulphur dichloride possesses the formula SCl_2 . At 60° , however, the reaction takes a different course, chlorobenzene and thianthrene being the products formed. This is attributed to the decomposition of sulphur dichloride into the monochloride and chlorine, the latter then attacking the benzene nucleus.

Beckmann and his collaborators (*Zeit. physikal. Chem.*, 1909, 65, 289) determined the molecular weights of the monochloride and the dichloride. They found that in liquid chlorine, at its boiling point, sulphur monochloride and sulphur dichloride have the molecular weights corresponding to the formulae S_2Cl_2 and SCl_2 respectively. They also arrived at the formula SCl_2 by means of cryoscopic determinations in xylene, *p*-xylene, ethylene dibromide, acetic acid and bromine solution. These results seem to have been confirmed by the work of Bergmann and Bloch (*Ber.*, 1920, 53, [B], 977).

Malonanilide and malon di-*o*-tolylamide interact with SCl_2 as follows :—

where R stands for the phenyl or the tolyl group.

In the case of both methyl-malonanilide and methyl-malon di-*o*-tolylamide only one hydrogen atom in the

reactive $-\text{CH}_2-$ group is available for interaction with sulphur dichloride, thus:—

where R represents either the phenyl or the tolyl group.

From the above it will be evident that the total negativity of the adjoining group, $\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{NHR}$ (where R is either phenyl or tolyl) which influences the reactivity of the hydrogens of the methylene group is practically the same, and hence the reaction should follow the same course. Experiments have justified this.

It also appears that both the hydrogens of the methylene group in compound (I) are simultaneously attacked by sulphur dichloride. This is in contrast with what happens in the case of sulphur monochloride, where one molecule of the substituted amide reacts with one molecule of sulphur monochloride and not two (Naik, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 379). Thus in the case of sulphur monochloride the reaction follows the course:—

where R is either the phenyl or tolyl group.

It is interesting to observe that, in general, the dithio-ketones obtained by the interaction of sulphur monochloride with some of the substituted amides are extremely stable (Naik, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 1231), whereas the compounds obtained by the action of sulphur dichloride are unstable, when treated with fuming nitric

acid. In the case of compound (I) the reaction proceeds as follows:—

where R_1 stands for phenylene or tolylene group.

The products obtained from malon di-*n*-propylamide and malon di-naphthylamides (α - and β -) belong to the same class. The reaction follows the course given below:—

(IV)

where R_1 stands for propyl group.

(V)

where R stands for α - or β -naphthyl group.

Here the total negativity of the group $\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{NHR}$ (where R is the propyl or naphthyl group) is reduced to a level which admits of the reactivity of only one of the hydrogens of the methylene group. In such cases it is but natural to expect the above course of the reaction.

These compounds are also unstable and lose all their sulphur and chlorine when nitrated, thus:—

where R_1 stands for naphthylene group.

Finally, in the cases of malon di-*p*-tolylamide, malon di-benzylamide and methyl-malon-di-*p*-tolylamide the reaction with sulphur dichloride proceeds further and very unstable compounds containing excess of chlorine are produced. In the case of methyl-malon-di-*p*-tolylamide the methyl group also is attacked, thus :—

where R is a *p*-tolyl or benzyl group.

The above products are stable only in a desiccator over sulphuric acid. In moist air they decompose, the original amide being obtained, with the evolution of hydrogen chloride and deposition of sulphur. It is interesting to observe that the tolyl compound (VI) on nitration loses all its sulphur and chlorine forming

The constitutions assigned to the above compounds follow from the following considerations :—

(1) That the hydrogen atom or atoms attacked by the dichloride are not those from the aromatic nuclei is evident from the course of the reaction in case (IV) where no such aromatic nuclei are present.

(2) The two hydrogen atoms eliminated are not those which were originally attached to the two nitrogen atoms ;

because, if that was so, the course of the reaction in every case ought to have been the same, for every one of the amides has two available $\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{NHR}$ groups.

(3) On reduction with alkaline hydrosulphide, say, in the case of (I), the original amide is obtained.

(4) That the original amide is obtained in the case of (VI) and (VII) in the presence of even a trace of moisture is sufficient to show that the reaction takes place with the hydrogens of the methylene group; because, if the interaction had taken place with the hydrogens of the aromatic nucleus, the substituted halogens could not be easily removed with water.

Apart from the light which the study of these reactions throws on the reactivity of the group, $\text{CO}\text{-CH}_2\text{-CO}$, another and a very important bearing of this work is in relation to the constitution of sulphur dichloride. The previous work done by one of us (Naik, *loc. cit.*) has tentatively shown that sulphur monochloride reacts in two forms :

and it is only in the case of (I) that stable disulphides are obtained. It was suggested in the beginning that sulphur dichloride is a mixture of monochloride and chlorine, or of tetrachloride and monochloride (*Ber.*, 1903, 36, 418). If this had been the case, in none of the above reactions could there have been a possibility of obtaining a definite class of compounds. The monochloride which was supposed to be one of the constituents which go to form the dichloride, ought to have contributed stable dithioketones, as was found out by Naik (*loc. cit.*).

The other constituent of sulphur dichloride, *viz.*, chlorine ought to have easily chlorinated the aromatic nucleus, and given aromatic chloro-compounds. But in no case were nuclei substituted halogen derivatives obtained. On the other hand, the compounds obtained possessed a separate identity of their own. It is, therefore, beyond doubt that sulphur dichloride did neither react as a mixture of sulphur monochloride and chlorine nor a mixture of sulphur tetrachloride and monochloride, but it is a definite chloride of sulphur having the formula SCl_2 .

EXPERIMENTAL.

The reactions were carried out in benzene solution. Under the conditions of the experiments there was no interaction between the solvent and the sulphur dichloride. In most cases the product of reaction separated from the cold solution in the crystalline form. Dry materials were always used, and when a reaction mixture had to be left overnight, precautions were taken against the entrance of moisture.

Sulphur Dichloride and Malon-anilide.

Malon anilide (3 g.) was mixed with dry benzene (20 c.c.), and sulphur dichloride (6g.) was added to the mixture. The reaction started at once and hydrochloric acid gas was evolved. The flask was corked with calcium chloride tube to avoid moisture and was left overnight. Next day it was heated under reflux over a sand-bath for four hours. As soon as benzene began to boil, copious fumes of hydrochloric acid gas were thrown out. The clear solution on standing deposited feathery needle-shaped crystals. They were filtered and washed with dry petroleum. They were found to be very soluble in acetic

acid, fairly soluble in alcohol, acetone, benzene and chloroform, sparingly soluble in light petroleum. On crystallisation from benzene the substance melted at 164-165°. (Found: Cl=18.69; S=16.72. $C_{15}H_{12}N_2O_2S_2Cl_2$ requires Cl=18.35; S=16.54 per cent.).

Nitration.—The compound (1 g.) was gradually added to fuming nitric acid (7 c.c.). Nitrogen peroxide came off and the mixture became hot. After some time air was blown into the acid to remove the fumes of nitrogen peroxide. The colourless liquid was then slowly added to water, when a yellow solid separated. It was filtered and washed completely with water. It shrank at 81° and melted with decomposition at 90°. (Found: N=16.10. $C_{15}H_{12}N_4O_6$ requires N=16.28 per cent.).

Sulphur Dichloride and Malon-di-o-tolylamide.

Malon-di-o-tolylamide (2 g.) was mixed with dry benzene (20 c.c.), and sulphur dichloride (5 g.) was added to the mixture. The reaction was vigorous and copious fumes of hydrogen chloride were formed. The mixture was refluxed over a sand-bath for three hours. On standing the clear liquid deposited white silky needles. They were filtered and washed with dry petroleum. They were soluble in benzene, alcohol, acetone, carbon tetrachloride and chloroform, and sparingly soluble in ether and petroleum. They were crystallised from hot benzene; m. p. 160-161°. (Found: Cl=17.34; S=15.55. $C_{17}H_{16}N_2O_2S_2Cl_2$ requires Cl=17.11; S=15.43 per cent.).

Reduction.—The substance (1 g.) was dissolved in alcohol, and 10 c.c. of an aqueous solution of sodium hydrogen sulphide (A solution was made by saturating 1.5 g. of caustic soda with hydrogen sulphide in a small quantity of water. To it caustic soda (5.7 g.) dissolved in a small quantity of water was added and the whole

made up to 30 c.c.) was gradually added to it, when a brown solution was obtained. The solution was diluted with water, and the solid obtained was washed with water. It was crystallised from glacial acetic acid; m. p. 190-191°. It contained neither chlorine nor sulphur and was identified as the original amide.

Nitroton.—The compound (1 g.) was gradually added to 10 c.c. of fuming nitric acid when fumes of nitrogen peroxide were thrown out. The liquid, after sometime, was warmed a little on a water-bath. After blowing air through the acid, the nearly colourless liquid was diluted with water and the reddish mass obtained was filtered and washed with cold water. It shrank at 75° and melted with decomposition at 85°. (Found: N=14.88. $C_{17}H_{19}O_6N_4$ requires N=15.05 per cent.).

Sulphur Dichloride and Methyl-malonanilide.

Methyl malonanilide (2 g.) was added to dry benzene (15 c.c.), and sulphur dichloride (4 g.) was then added to it. The reaction mixture was finished up as in the preceding case. The solid was soluble in acetic acid, alcohol, acetone, benzene and chloroform, and sparingly soluble in ether and petroleum; m. p. 132°. (Found: Cl=10.39; S=9.27. $C_{16}H_{15}N_2O_2S_2Cl$ requires Cl=10.61; S=9.56 per cent.).

Sulphur Dichloride and Methyl-malon-di-o-tolylamide.

Methyl-malon-di-o-tolylamide (2 g.) was put in 15 c.c. of dry benzene and sulphur dichloride (4 g.) was added to it. The reaction mixture was heated under reflux over a sand-bath for three hours, after keeping it at ordinary temperature for some time. On standing, some crystals were deposited and more solid was obtained on dilution

with dry petroleum. The mass was crystallised from benzene; m. p. 150° (Found: Cl=9.39; S=8.69. $C_{18}H_{19}N_2O_2SCl$ requires Cl=9.79; S=8.82 per cent.).

Sulphur Dichloride and Malon-di- α -naphthylamide.

Malon di- α -naphthylamide (3 g.) was added to 20 c.c. of dry benzene. Sulphur dichloride (7 g.) dissolved in a little benzene was then added to the mixture. After some time, the mixture was refluxed over a sand-bath for three hours when hydrogen chloride ceased to evolve. When benzene began to boil, the liquid assumed green colour. On standing the solution deposited a solid which was filtered and washed with dry petroleum. The white mass soon began to be blue on the surface. It was therefore put in a desiccator. It was crystallised from benzene. It became blue. It was soluble in acetic acid, acetone, benzene and carbon tetrachloride, and sparingly soluble in ether and petroleum. It melted with decomposition at 145° . (Found: Cl=8.63; S=8.09. $C_{23}H_{17}N_2O_2SCl$ requires Cl=8.44; S=7.6 per cent.).

Sulphur Dichloride and Malon-di- β -naphthylamide.

The amide (5 g.) was added to 50 c.c. of dry benzene and sulphur dichloride (10 g.) was added to it. Hydrogen chloride was at once thrown out. The mixture was refluxed over a sand-bath for four hours, but the product was insoluble in benzene. On cooling the solid was filtered and washed. It was sparingly soluble in alcohol, acetone and ether, and fairly soluble in boiling acetic acid, from which it came down as an amorphous yellowish powder. It melted with decomposition at 230° — 31° . (Found: Cl=8.55; S=7.37. $C_{23}H_{17}N_2O_2SCl$ requires Cl=8.44; S=7.61 per cent.).

Nitration.—The compound (1 g.) was gradually added to 10 c.c. of fuming nitric acid. Copious fumes of nitrogen peroxide were thrown out. The mixture was heated on a water-bath for some time and then air was blown into the hot mixture to remove the fumes. It was then diluted with cold water and the yellowish solid obtained was filtered and washed. It shrank at 175° and melted with decomposition at 185° . (Found: N=12.45. $C_{22}H_{16}N_4O_6$ requires N=12.6 per cent.).

Sulphur Dichloride and Malon-di-n-propylamide.

The amide (2 g.) was added to 25 c.c. of dry benzene and sulphur dichloride (4 g.) was then added to it. The reaction started at once and the reaction mixture became hot. The flask was corked with a calcium chloride tube and left overnight. Next day it was refluxed over a sand-bath for about an hour and then concentrated, when a solid was deposited. It was filtered and washed with dry petroleum. On slow evaporation of petroleum the white solid began to smell of hydrochloric acid and became pasty. It was then placed in a desiccator over caustic soda for several days. Afterwards it was crystallised from dry benzene and the solid was washed with a mixture of ether and petroleum. It is soluble in alcohol and benzene, and sparingly soluble in chloroform, ether and petroleum; m. p. $141-142^{\circ}$. (Found: Cl=13.80; S=12.50. $C_9H_{17}N_2O_2S$ Cl requires Cl=14.06; S=12.67 per cent.).

Sulphur Dichloride and Malon-di-p-tolylamide.

The amide (4 g.) was mixed with 25 c.c. of dry benzene and sulphur dichloride (8 g.) was added to the mixture. The reaction started at once with the evolution of hydrogen chloride. The flask was corked with a

calcium chloride tube and left overnight at room temperature. Next day it was refluxed over a sand-bath for about four hours. On cooling the clear solution deposited white crystals which were filtered and washed with dry petroleum. They were soluble in acetic acid, alcohol, acetone, benzene, carbon disulphide and chloroform. The solid was crystallised from benzene; m. p. 158°. (Found: Cl=18.16; S=8.78. $C_{17}H_{16}N_2O_2SCl_2$ requires Cl=18.54; S=8.35 per cent.).

The compound when put in ordinary air was found to smell of hydrochloric acid after some days. This went on for about two months, after which period the compound assumed a yellowish tint. It was insoluble in benzene and was crystallised from glacial acetic acid; m. p. 247°. It was found to contain neither sulphur nor chlorine and was identified as the original amide. The compound is stable when put in a desiccator over concentrated sulphuric acid.

Nitration:—The compound (1 g.) was gradually added to 8 c.c. of fuming nitric acid. Fumes of nitrogen peroxide were thrown out when the substance was being added. After some time air was blown into the acid and the nearly colourless solution was diluted with water, when a yellow mass was obtained. It shrank at 85° and melted with decomposition at 120°. (Found: N=14.72. $C_{17}H_{16}N_4O_6$ requires N=15.05 per cent.).

Sulphur Dichloride and Malon-di-benzylamide.

The amide (3 g.) was taken with 25 c.c. of dry benzene and sulphur dichloride (6 g.) was added to the mixture. The reaction mixture was corked with a calcium chloride tube and left overnight at room temperature. Next day it was refluxed over a sand-bath for six

hours when hydrogen chloride ceased to evolve. The clear solution on standing deposited white silky needle-shaped crystals. They were filtered and washed with dry petroleum. They were soluble in acetic acid, alcohol, acetone, benzene and chloroform. The mass was crystallised from boiling benzene, m. p. 149—150°. (Found: Cl=18.26; S=8.82. $C_{17}H_{16}N_2O_2SCl_2$ requires Cl=18.54; S=8.35 per cent.).

This product also decomposed as in the case of malon di-*p*-tolylamide and the original amide was obtained in this case too.

Sulphur Dichloride and Methyl-malon-di-p-tolylamide.

The amide (4 g.) was put in 25 c.c. of dry benzene and sulphur dichloride (8 g.) was added to the mixture. The flask was corked with a calcium chloride tube and left overnight at room temperature. Next day it was refluxed over a sand-bath for three hours. The clear solution on standing deposited crystals. They were filtered and washed with dry petroleum. They were soluble in acetic acid, alcohol, benzene, acetone and chloroform, and sparingly soluble in ether and petroleum. The mass was crystallised from benzene, m. p. 157—158°. (Found: Cl=18.23; S=7.88. $C_{18}H_{18}N_2O_2SCl_2$ requires Cl=17.88; S=8.06 per cent.).

This compound also decomposed as in the two previous cases. The decomposition product was insoluble in benzene and therefore it was crystallised from glacial acetic acid, m. p. 240°. It was identified as the original amide. The compound was stable when put in a desiccator over concentrated sulphuric acid.